

Synthesis of Sulphur and Nitrogen Heterocyclics Involving Rearrangement *Via* Small Rings*

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It is indeed a great honour to be called upon to deliver the Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture (1978). I am grateful to the Indian Chemical Society for conferring on me this distinction.

Acharya Ray not only founded the Indian Chemical Society but was also the father of Indian Chemistry and Chemical Industry. I pay my humble homage to this great man to whom the nation owes so much.

In this lecture, I wish to briefly cover my work over the last twenty years, pertaining to the synthesis of sulphur and nitrogen heterocyclics, wherein we came across rearrangements which could be rationally explained by postulating the involvement of small (three or four membered) sulphur and nitrogen ring systems. In a few cases compounds representing these small ring systems were also isolated or

synthesised and then isomerized to five and six membered heterocyclics in a two step sequence.

The general method of synthesis of sulphur and nitrogen heterocyclics involved cyclodehydration of suitably substituted ketones or carbinols where the carbonyl and hydroxyl groups involved in the cyclodehydration reaction were removed from the hetero atom by one or two carbon atoms (*via* a methylene, dimethylene group or a double bond). The end products were the expected cyclodehydration products as well as the rearrangement products where the substituents attached to the carbonyl/hydroxyl group carrying carbon atoms and those attached to the carbon atoms linked directly to the hetero atom in the aliphatic chain were found to be interchanged. The general scheme of these reactions is shown in Chart 1. Synthesis of other sulphur/nitrogen heterocyclics arising out of the general schemes shown in Chart 1 are also described.

Synthesis of 5-membered sulphur heterocyclics via thiiranium salts:

Cyclodehydration of phenacyl phenyl sulphide 1 and its derivatives, (by treatment with PPA) was reported earlier¹ to give mostly 2-phenylthionaphthene 2. We however showed that the reaction gave both the 2-phenyl 2 (47%) as well as 3-phenylthionaphthene 3 (15%)². Earlier reports¹ on cyclodehydration of phenacyl *p*-toluyl sulphide 4

$X = -S-, -NH-$
 $X_1 = -S^+, -N=$
 ClO_2^-
 $R_1, R_2 = \text{Alkyl/Aryl groups}$
Chart 1

Chart 2

* Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture (1978) delivered under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society at Pune on 21st December, 1981.

were likewise revised by us² to show that the reaction gave both the expected 5-methyl-3-phenylthionaphthene 5 (25%) as well as the rearranged 5-methyl-2-phenylthionaphthene 6 (36%). The formation of the rearranged cyclodehydration products 2 and 6 in the above reactions was explained by us by postulating the intermediate formation of the three-membered sulphur heterocyclic intermediate, a thiiranium salt 7 which then ring expands in two alternative ways to yield the two sets of thionaphthenes 3, 5, (normal products) and 2, 6, (rearranged products)² (Chart 2).

Similarly, cyclodehydration of 2-thionaphthacyl phenyl sulphide 8 with P₂O₅ or PPA gave both the normal cyclodehydration product 2,3'-dithionaphthene 9 as well as 2,2'-dithionaphthene 10³ which probably arises by rearrangement *via* the relevant thiiranium salt reactive intermediate 11 (Chart 3).

Chart 3

Several more such rearrangements were also reported by us during the cyclodehydration of other

Chart 4

aroylmethyl aryl sulphides^{4,5}. Most of them led to two sets of arylthionaphthenes, one the normally expected cyclodehydration product and the other the rearrangement product (Chart 4). These rearrangements could also be explained on the basis of involvement of reactive thiiranium salts as reactive intermediates.

It is interesting to note that cyclodehydration of α -phenylmercaptopropiophenone 26 with PPA gave only the normally expected 3-phenyl-2-methylthionaphthene 27 and the rearranged product 2-phenyl-3-methylthionaphthene 28 could not be traced⁴. However, in the light of more sophisticated techniques of analysis and separation now available it is desirable to re-examine these results (Chart 5).

Chart 5

The above rearrangements, observed during cyclodehydration of aroylmethyl aryl sulphides, have also been found to occur in the acid catalysed cyclodehydration of aroylmethyl aryl ethers and aroylmethylarylamines (or secondary amines) 29 where also both the normally expected benzofurans and indoles 30 and the rearranged cyclodehydration products 31 are formed^{6,7} (Chart 6). Several other rearrangement reactions in the synthesis of benzo-*b*-thiophenes during acid-catalysed cyclodehydrations of relevant keto-sulphides are also reported⁸. All these rearrangements probably occur through three-

Chart 6

The involvement of a thiiranium salt 33 and N,N-dialkylaziridinium salt 34 is widely recognized in explaining the biological activity (as alkylating agents) of mustard gas and nitrogen mustards. We had also suggested the possible involvement of

thiurium salts 35 and 36 to account for the carcinostatic activity found by us for thiodiglycol and thiodiglycolic acid⁹ (Chart 7).

Chart 7

Acid catalysed cyclodehydration of β -hydroxyalkyl aryl sulphides 37 also gave both the normal 2,3-dihydrobenzo-*b*-thiophenes 38 as well as the rearranged thiophenes 39. Here also the rearrangement products are obviously formed via the reactive intermediate S-arylthiurium salts 40 (Chart 8). In a few cases these reactive intermediates 40 were also isolated and then isomerized to the two sets of products 38 and 39^{10,11}. The ratios of the normal and rearranged 2,3-dihydrobenzo-*b*-thiophenes and the proportion of *cis-trans* isomers obtained are also shown in Chart 8.

Chart 8

Synthesis of sulphur heterocyclics containing bridge-head sulphonium salt moiety :

Apart from the above thiurium salts, we have also synthesised several five- and six-membered heterocyclic sulphonium salts, in some of which heterocyclic sulphur occupies a bridge-head position¹²⁻¹⁵. The synthesis of some of these sulphur and nitrogen heterocyclics involves rearrangement of incipient carbonium ions by 1,2-alkyl or proton shifts¹²⁻¹⁴ (Chart 9).

Chart 9

Synthesis of six-membered sulphur heterocycles via S-arylthiacyclobutanium and S-arylthiacyclobutenium salts :

Rearrangement reactions occurring through reactive three-membered heterocyclic intermediates described above were also observed during the synthesis of six-membered sulphur and nitrogen heterocyclic compounds through acid-catalysed cyclodehydration of appropriately substituted ketones and carbinols. Here also the rearrangement most probably occurs through reactive four-membered sulphur and nitrogen heterocyclic ring systems which then ring expand in two alternative ways to give the observed products. In several cases the relevant reactive four-membered sulphur and nitrogen heterocyclic compounds were also isolated and then isomerized to six-membered ring systems, the observed products of cyclodehydration reactions.

Thus, cyclodehydration of both β -phenylmercaptoethyl methyl ketone 49 and β -phenyl- β -phenylmercaptoethyl methyl ketone 50 gave a mixture of two sets of thianaphthalenium salts 51 and 52 and the thiachromans 53 and 54 in different proportions. The fact that all the four compounds are obtained starting from two different starting β -arylmercaptoethyl ketones, 49 and 50, goes to show that the cyclodehydration probably occurs through four-membered saturated (S-phenylthiacyclobutanium

salts) **57**, **58** or unsaturated (S-phenylthiacyclobutonium salts) **63**, **64** sulphur ring systems as shown in Chart 10. The hydroxycyclobutanium salts **57**, **58** are obviously unstable and readily yield S-phenylcyclobutenium salts **63**, **64** which were isolated in several cases and then isomerized to the six-membered sulphur ring systems, the observed products of cyclodehydration of the β -arylmethyl ketones. Depending on the nature of substituents (R_1 , R_2), **63** or **64** are more stable (in acidic solutions) and the less stable thiacyclobutenium salt is slowly converted to the more stable thiacyclobutenium salt¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Consequently, the relative proportion of the normal as against the rearranged products in the above cyclodehydration reactions will depend on the nature of substituents R_1 and R_2 and the relative stability of the incipient carbonium ions involved in the cyclization step.

Proton abstraction from the yellow coloured thiacyclobutenium salts, **63** and **64**, by treatment with sodium hydride, gave an identical olive green coloured neutral compound which is assigned a ylid (in preference to thiacyclobutadiene) structure as shown in Chart 10A. Reprotonation of the ylid yields the more stable of the two thiacyclobutenium salt **63** or **64**¹⁷. Whereas these ylids could not be isolated and were unstable, several stable neutral sulphur heterocyclics, containing S(IV) atom, were prepared by us rather simply by thionation of appropriately substituted 1,8-dichloroanthraquinones and 1,4,5,8-tetrachloroanthraquinone. These are deeply coloured (red to green) quinonoid compo-

unds some of which are used commercially as vat dyes for cotton^{18,4} (Chart 10A).

Cyclodehydration of β -arylmethyl ketones **65** by means of perchloric acid gave

Chart 11

essentially the rearranged thianaphalenium perchlorate **66** and only smaller amounts of the normal product **67**. It seems likely that the rearranged products are formed through the intermediacy of reactive hydroxythiacyclobutenium perchlorates, **68**, **69**, which then lead to observed products **66**, **67** (Chart 11)¹⁹. Several complex linear and angular polycyclic thianaphalenium perchlorates were synthesised by this general method. In most cases cyclodehydration of the β -arylmethylmercaptomethylene ketones gave only the rearranged thianaphalenium perchlorates (Chart 11)¹⁹.

Cyclodehydration of 1-phenyl-1-phenylmercaptoethyl-3-butanol **71**, obtained by NaBH₄ reduction of β -phenyl- β -phenylmercaptoethyl methyl ketone **70**, by treatment with perchloric acid yields mostly the rearranged 2-methyl-4-phenylthiachroman¹⁸ **72**. The formation of the latter rearranged product is also explicable on the basis of intermediate involvement of 1-S-phenyl-1-thiocyclobutanium salt **73** (Chart 12). However, attempts to synthesise the latter compounds have not been successful so far.

Chart 12

Synthesis of quinolines via azetidines and azetines :

In analogy with the above acid catalysed cyclodehydration reactions, 1-arylamino-3-alkanols **74** gave both the normal **75** as well as the rearranged **76** tetrahydroquinolines^{20,21}. The formation of the rearranged tetrahydroquinolines **76** is explicable by postulating the intermediate involvement of N-arylazetidines **77** which on ring expansion lead to **75** and/or **76** depending on the nature of substituents and their stereochemistry¹⁸. The relevant N-arylazetidines were also synthesised from the corresponding carbinols **74** by cyclodehydration with sulphuric acid²² or better with triphenylphosphine dibromide in presence of triethylamine²³. Stereospecific synthesis of the azetidines and their stereo-selective

Chart 13

conversion to *cis*- or *trans*-tetrahydroquinolines has also been achieved¹⁸ (Chart 13).

Cyclodehydration of β -arylaminoethyl alkyl/cycloalkyl/aryl ketones **78** by treatment with fused zinc chloride and an arylamine hydrochloride in boiling ethanol gave a mixture of rearranged quinolines **79** and tetrahydroquinolines **80** alongwith the normal cyclodehydration products **81**, **82**. The formation of rearranged products is explicable by envisaging the intermediate formation of N-arylazetidines **83** or through the involvement of N-arylazetines^{18,24,25}, **84**, **85** as shown in Chart 14.

Chart 14

Cyclodehydration of β -arylaminoethyl aryl

L = Leaving group e.g. ArNH₂, OH, -Lactate, -O-ZnCl
Chart 15

ketones **86** by treatment with PPA gave in most cases the relevant quinolines²⁶ **87**, whereas treatment of **86** with arylamine hydrochloride and fused zinc chloride in boiling ethanol, chloroacetic acid, lactic acid, ethanolic hydrochloric acid or perchloric acid gave the rearranged quinolines **88**. The rearrangement may be taking place through reactive intermediate azetines **89**, **90** (Chart 15) although other plausible mechanisms have also been suggested²⁵. A large number of quinolines of the general formulae **87**, **88** have been synthesised by us^{25,26} (Chart 16). Attempts to isolate or to synthesise N-arylazetines of the type **89**, **90**, however, proved unsuccessful. There is also no report in literature of the synthesis of N-arylazetines.

Chart 16

Several complex sulphur and nitrogen containing heterocyclic compounds were also synthesised by cyclodehydration of the relevant β -arylaminoethylene ketones where also the heterocyclics were obtained through rearrangement, possibly through the relevant azetines²⁷⁻³¹. Some of these syntheses are shown in Chart 17 by way of illustration.

Synthesis of 3,4-dihydro-1,3,2-oxazaphosphorin-2-oxides and their rearrangement to quinolines :

In view of the synthesis of S-arylcyclobutenium perchlorates by interaction of β -arylaminoethylene ketones with $\text{POCl}_3/\text{HClO}_4$ discussed earlier, β -arylaminoethyl aryl ketones **91** were treated with POCl_3 and later (or simultaneously) with triethylamine. Instead of the expected azetines, **92**

Chart 17

Chart 18

2-chloro-3, 6-diaryl-3, 4-dihydro-1, 3, 2-oxazaphosphorin-2-oxides **93** were formed readily through intermediate phosphoramides **94**, which were also isolated in a few cases (Chart 18). Four compounds in this series **93** were found to be active against P388 lymphocytic leukemia³². Whereas tetrahydro-1,3,2-oxazaphosphorin-2-oxides (cyclophosphamides) are widely studied and some of them (e.g, Endoxan) are well known and widely used anti-leukemic agents, the 3,4-dihydro-1,3,2-oxazaphosphorin-2-oxides **93** represent new O,N,P, heterocyclic ring system. These compounds are very stable to heat, light, hydrolytic cleavage and dilute acids and alkali. The chlorine atom in **93** is, however, replaced by secondary alkylamino, azido, ethoxy and hydroxy (in the presence of phase transfer catalysts) groups to give 2-substituted-3,6-diaryl-3,4-dihydro-1,3,2-oxazaphosphorin-2-oxides **95**.

The oxazaphosphorin **96** was slowly converted on keeping to 7-methoxy-4-phenylquinoline **97** in high yield (90%). The transformation was rapid on photolysis, acid treatment or heating in benzene with or without Et₃N. Some 7-methoxy-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline **98** (yield 6%) was also formed. This transformation seems to be specific for **96** since other oxazaphosphorins **93**, **95** failed to give the corresponding quinoline derivatives (Chart 18). The mechanism of this facile conversion of **96** to **97** in high yield, even in *absence* of air, is under investigation.

Synthesis of azepines through nitrene insertion :

Thermal decomposition of *p*-toluenesulphonylazide **99** with benzenoid substrates containing electronegative substituents such as carbomethoxy, nitro, cyano, acetyl, dicarbomethoxy or dicarbomethoxy groups yielded the azepines **104** and *p*-toluenesulphonamido derivatives **103**, of which the former are formed in greater (*albiet* low) yield^{33,34}. The formation of azepines involves the addition of thermally generated (singlet) nitrene **100** across the double bond carrying the electro-negative substituent. Ring expansion of the resulting unstable aziridines **102** then yields the relevant azepines **104** (Chart 19).

Chart 19

Thermal interaction of **99** with dimethyl phthalate and anthraquinone gave the azepines **105** and **106** and *p*-toluenesulphonamidoanthraquinone **107**³⁵ (Chart 20).

Chart 20

Although the yield of the above azepines were generally very low (5-20%), in view of the inaccessibility of these complex azepines by other methods, the present work may be of some interest.

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